

Good Practices of Media and Information Literacy in Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia

in line with the findings of the Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy

Credit: Daniela Eckl

Media and information literacy is fundamental to pro-democratic media policy. This is evident from the resolutions adopted by the four Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy, held in Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia between March and May 2025.

Citizens' parliaments on Media and Democracy were organised as part of the project **Mapping Media for Future Democracies** (MeDeMAP), involving partners from academia and civil society in ten EU countries. All teams examined the relationship between media and democracy and citizens' demand for more participation. The research project was coordinated by the Austrian Academy of Sciences (OEAW) and funded by the Horizon Europe programme.

Each of the Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy comprised 20 citizens. These were organised by COMMIT (Austria), Charles University (Czech Republic), Mary Immaculate College (Ireland) and the Peace Institute (Slovenia). During four sessions dedicated to the topics of media and democracy, systems, representation, and participation, the citizens adopted resolutions in support of media policies that would strengthen democracy in their respective countries. Further details of the sessions can be found on the Citizens' Parliaments' blog

<https://medemap.commit.at/medemap-blog/>

Media and Information Literacy is the ability to access, analyse, evaluate and create messages in a variety of contexts. It helps discern bias, recognize misinformation, resist hate speech, and actively engage in civic life, promoting informed decision-making in today's complex digital world (UNESCO).

Media literacy should not be limited to learning about tools and technologies, but should aim to equip people with the critical thinking skills required to exercise judgment, analyse complex realities and recognise the difference between opinion and fact. (EC 2023)

In line with the resolutions adopted by the Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy, examples of good practice in media and information literacy are presented from **Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia**.

Austria

*Acknowledging the significance of information and media literacy in fostering civic engagement, the **Austrian Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy** adopted five resolutions aimed at promoting media literacy among all age groups.*

WIENXTRA-Medienzentrum – media education and youth work

The Medienzentrum is part of Vienna's youth services and supports young people aged 10 to 22 in realising their own media projects. It offers workshops, advice, equipment rental, studios and editing rooms free of charge to young people and young professionals. The Medienzentrum also offers media education training for young people on a variety of topics.

Medienzentrum for youth workers

<https://wienextra.at/medienzentrum/>

<https://wienextra.at/jugendarbeit/informationen/themen-highlights/thema/medienbildung-und-digitale-jugendarbeit/>

COMMIT – Community Medien Institute

COMMIT connects community media with adult education. It offers a variety of formats for teaching critical media literacy to media professionals and adult education trainers. These range from short webinars to multi-day courses within the framework of political education.

COMMIT <https://www.commit.at>

COMMIT also provides learners with access to a wide range of freely available materials.

Media.Law.Ethics

<https://www.commit.at/materialien/handreichungen-und-schulungsunterlagen/medienrechtethik>

The Czech Republic

*The **Czech Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy** adopted eight resolutions on media and information literacy. They call for a structured media literacy policy for all, as well as funding for organisations dedicated to media literacy. The Czech Republic is a member of the Central European Digital Media Observatory (CEDMO).*

One World in Schools (JSNS) - Media Education in Primary Schools

One World in Schools (JSNS), a project by People in Need, focuses on media education in primary and secondary schools by offering comprehensive audiovisual lessons, teacher training, and interactive seminars. Over 4,000 schools utilize JSNS resources to boost media literacy and critical thinking about information quality, fake news, and social issues. The project organises "Media Literacy Weeks", which includes a day-long educational and networking event called the Media Education Fair.

JSNS - One World in Schools <https://www.jsns.cz/en/projects/media-education-in-primary-schools>

People in Need - Media Literacy Weeks <https://www.peopleinneed.net/jsns-media-literacy-weeks-educational-events-discussions-with-journalists-and-materials-for-teachers-11431gp>

Safer Internet Centrum ČR - Internet safety and digital literacy

The Safer Internet Centrum ČR (SIC CZ) is dedicated to promoting internet safety and digital literacy across the country. The center operates through three pillars: prevention (educational programs for children, teachers, parents), helplines (24/7 crisis lines for those facing online risks), and a hotline for reporting illegal digital content. Operating as part of European networks (Insafe and INHOPE), SIC CZ partners with organizations like JSNS to deliver workshops and public awareness campaigns targeting online risks. It is an official partner of the European Commission for Safer Internet topics.

Safer Internet Center <https://www.bezpecnyinternet.cz/en/about-us/>

EU- Better Internet for Kids <https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/sic/czech-republic>

Fakescape - Teaching media literacy through games

Developed by students from Masaryk University in 2018, Fakescape creates educational games designed to help participants recognize fake news and strengthen critical thinking. The games are tailored for primary and secondary school students, as well as adults. It aims to promote media literacy across different age and demographic groups in a playful, interactive way.

Fakescape <https://fakescape.cz/en/fakescape-en/>

Ireland

The Irish Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy has expressed concern that audiences may not be sufficiently protected or informed to engage fully in the country's democratic processes, or to make critical judgements. The members adopted several resolutions to promote media literacy for all, emphasising the importance of responsible digital citizenship.

Media Literacy Ireland

Media Literacy Ireland is an independent association committed to promoting media literacy across Ireland. It is funded by Ireland's media regulator, Coimisiún na Meán. The association has over 250 volunteer members, including representatives from NGOs, academia, and teachers.

Media Literacy Ireland provides individuals, teachers, youth workers and trainers with advice on how to counter disinformation and protect themselves and others. It aims to empower people to access and critically evaluate content and services across all platforms so they can participate effectively in the public sphere. The association runs courses and advertising campaigns on national and social media.

Media Literacy Ireland <https://www.medialiteracyireland.ie/>

The Media Literacy (MLI) Awards recognise efforts to empower citizens, particularly those within communities, to develop their media literacy skills. The awards are supported by Coimisiún na Meán.

<https://www.medialiteracyireland.ie/awards/>

Algowatch received the MLI award for the Best Media Literacy Initiative for Young People in 2025. This European project focuses on educating the general public about the challenges of algorithms and artificial intelligence in relation to information and digital citizenship.

<https://algowatch.eu/>

The Media Literacy Ireland Conference 2025 – Supporting communities, fostering citizenship, promoting democracy

The Media Literacy Ireland Conference, which took place in Dublin in November 2025, focused on 'Supporting Communities, Fostering Citizenship, Promoting Democracy'. The event provided an opportunity for networking and the exchange of ideas across the media literacy community. It also welcomed international speakers from Germany, Ukraine and Moldova. Over 90 people from various sectors across Ireland attended, including members of the Webwise youth panel who offered valuable insights into the views of young people.

<https://www.medialiteracyireland.ie/the-media-literacy-ireland-conference-2025/>

Slovenia

The Slovenian Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy has emphasised that media literacy should be strengthened at every stage of formal education, supported by teacher training and integrated across subjects, and complemented by tailored programmes for adults and other groups outside schools. It has also urged national and European authorities, as well as media outlets themselves, to foster media literacy and citizen empowerment to improve participation in democratic life.

Časoris - News for children and youth

Časoris is a non-profit online media outlet that produces news and explanatory journalism specifically for children and young people. The content is written in accessible language, contextualised for younger audiences and often accompanied by educational materials for use in schools. The outlet helps young readers to develop critical reading habits in a safe, age-appropriate media environment.

Časoris <https://casoris.si>

Državljan D – Media literacy workshops for youth

Državljan D implements workshops for young people that focus on critical media consumption, understanding power relations in digital platforms, and recognising misinformation, hate speech, and manipulation. The workshops combine practical examples from everyday media use with participatory discussion formats, encouraging youth to reflect on their own role as media users and potential content creators.

Državljan D <https://www.drzavljand.si>

AKOS (The Agency for Communication Networks and Services of the Republic of Slovenia) – Media and information literacy portal (MIPI)

Coordinated by the Agency for Communication Networks and Services of the Republic of Slovenia (AKOS), the Media and Information Literacy Portal (MIPI) serves as a central public resource for media literacy education. It brings together educational materials, research, tools and examples of good practice for educators, parents, journalists and the general public. The portal promotes cross-sector collaboration and guarantees the long-term availability of reliable, high-quality media literacy resources.

MIPI <https://www.mipi.si>

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